

A Comparative Analysis of the performance of the LSTM Network and ARIMA Model for the forecasting of a non-stationary financial time-series

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Abstract- Forecasting the stock-market is an age-old requirement in an investor's tool-kit for successful investments. The stock market is affected by various factors that include (but are not limited to) sentiments, demand, supply, policy, political climate, among others. This makes predicting the dynamics of the stock market an incredibly challenging task. It is a combination of both random and deterministic phenomena. For this task, a variety of deep-learning and stochastic models have been developed. This paper attempts to compare two of the most used predictive models: LSTM-RNN and ARIMA over data collected from State Bank of India's historical stock price.

Key Words: Stock-Market, Prediction, Forecasting, Deep-Learning, ARIMA, LSTM

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been believed for quite some time now that the efficient-market hypothesis (EMH) is not entirely correct [1]. Stock prices of most (if not all) public organisations and companies fluctuate regularly. These fluctuations can be caused by various factors outside the control of the company's performance like Public Sector Undertakings, GDP trends of the country, Foreign Exchange Rate, public policies and Oil Prices [2]. Due to this, neural networks have proved to be an excellent method to model and analyse financial time-series, as they are able to learn and process various factors by themselves [3]. On the other hand, stochastic models like ARIMA (Auto-Regression Integrated Moving Average) are also a viable option for time-series that display stationarity (in that, they are independent of the time at which they are observed). For forecasting financial time-series using LSTM-RNN (Recurrent Neural Network), this paper utilises the Keras library. For proper implementation of the ARIMA model, we use the work-flow prescribed by M. Angadi, A. Kulkarni, in [4].

2. RELEVANT LITERATURE

A variety of papers on individual forecasting models like LSTM and ARIMA already exist.

Authors of [5] provide evidence for the practicality and effectiveness of the LSTM model compared to SVMs and Backpropagation in forecasting time-series data.

In [6], the authors conclusively assert the accuracy and implications of using the ARIMA model for stock price prediction. This is a useful work that renders the absolute importance of stochastic processes in the market.

In [7], the authors provide a detailed account of the multitude of machine-learning models ranging from SVMs to LSTMs that can be useful in our endeavour.

3. METHODOLOGIES AND WORK-PROCESS

Even though a variety of APIs give the feature of importing historical stock prices and data in a CSV format, this paper utilises Yahoo Finance's historical data collection for reliable results. This paper uses comma-separated value (CSV) data of State Bank of India's stock price from 13-03-2015 to today for both the ARIMA and LSTM model. This data consists of any stock's seven primary characteristics that include Volume, Opening Price and Closing Price, among others. For simplicity, and to also limit the scope of our models to one-dimensional space, we will train our models on only the closing price of SBI's stock.

3.1 Preprocessing of Data

As in any dataset, our dataset consists of a variety of abnormalities which may result in Linear Algebra errors for ARIMA and exploding gradients for LSTM. For this, we drop all the null-values from our dataset and convert it into a simple array of the stock's closing prices. This technique is widely used and can also be seen in [8]. Other than cleaning the data for proper training, to make the process efficient, we also normalise, denoise and transform the data. This also helps us avoid erroneous output.

3.2 Check for Stationarity

While stationarity is not necessary for our LSTM model, it is a requirement (and a limitation) of the ARIMA model. To check for stationarity, we use the wide-spread Dickey-Fuller Test. On running the significance test on our data, we find that the data is indeed non-stationary.

Adam because it is known to be effective with non-stationary data[11].

Fig -5: Architecture of LSTM (source: colah.github.io)

3.8 Evaluating the LSTM Model

Our LSTM Model proves to be very useful in the modelling of stock prices. It has an accuracy of about 89%, which is an incredible improvement from the ARIMA model, which failed despite a confidence-interval of 95%. A variety of reasons caused this increment, and one is ARIMA's limitation itself when it comes to the analysis of non-stationary data. Furthermore, our seasonal decomposition method may have also had a vital role in the ARIMA model's poor performance.

4. Graphical Results

We provide the graphical results for the predictions made by the two models. This is for greater intuition about the polarity in the effectiveness of the two models.

Fig -5: Prediction of the ARIMA Model (Scaled)

Fig -6: Predictions of the LSTM Model

5. CONCLUSIONS

After a detailed analysis of the error-graphs of both the models and a clear depiction through the forecast graphs, we can with reasonable certainty conclude that for non-stationary time-series, LSTM networks perform significantly better than other stochastic models like ARIMA. This gives us an insight into the further scope of Neural Networks' application in forecasting stock-prices as most if not all, trends in the financial market are non-stationary and non-seasonal.

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